

Role of water in the development of new isocyanate-based bituminous products. *Industrial and Engineering Chemistry Research*, 47(18), 6933-6940

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Abstract

Asphalt, roofing, and sealing markets strongly demand new materials for being used, for instance, as bituminous coating membranes. In that sense, this paper deals with the effect on these bitumen-based composites of the addition of a MDI-PEG reactive polymer, synthesized by the reaction of 4,4'-diphenylmethane diisocyanate with a low molecular weight poly(ethylene glycol). A short-term modification, taking place during mixing, and a long-term bitumen modification, which develops for a long period of curing (up to several months), have been identified. Both of them result from chemical reactions between NCO groups in the MDI-PEG and some of the bitumen compounds, mainly, the resin fraction. However, long-term bitumen modification seems to be related to the polymer-bitumen reactions but influenced by the environmental conditions (probably due to air moisture). This fact may be used to improve the manufacture of new materials with suitable properties according to their final application.

Keywords: Bitumen. MDI-PEG. Rheology

F 1. Evolution of the normalized torque (M/M_0) with time during processing of different bitumen/MDI-PEG/water blends, at 90 °C and 60 rpm.

F 2. Viscous flow curves, at 60 °C, for a selected 2 wt % MDI-PEG modified bitumen, as a function of curing time (A), and for samples with different MDI-PEG concentrations after a curing period of 15 days (B)

F 3. Reversing (A) and nonreversing (B) heat flow thermograms, as a function of curing time, for a selected polymer modified bitumen (8 wt % MDI-PEG)

F 4. Evolution of the NCO band, obtained by FTIR at 2273 cm^{-1} , with curing time for a selected 8 wt % MDI-PEG modified bitumen

F 5. Evolution of the SARAs fractions with curing time for a selected 8 wt % MDI-PEG modified bitumen

F 6. Frequency dependence of the storage and loss moduli, at temperatures between -20 and 120 °C, for 8 wt % MDI-PEG modified bitumen samples taken from the top and bottom of the container, after 4 months of storage

F 8. Black diagrams for the same samples as F6

F 7. Nonreversing heat flow thermograms for 10 wt % MDI-PEG modified bitumen samples taken from the top and bottom of the container, after 6 months storage

F 9. Viscous flow curves, at 60 °C, for the same systems showed in Figure 1, after 0 (A) and 50 days (B) curing